

APPENDIX – Quality Assessment

Quality Assessment Form

Quality Criteria	0	0,5	1
QC1: Are the Inclusion and Exclusion criteria well described and appropriate?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
QC2: Did the literature research potentially include all the relevant studies?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
QC3: Did the included studies have their quality/validity assessed?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
QC4: Has the database/study base been adequately described?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Quality Assessment

Reference of the secondary studies	ID	1	2	3	4	TOTAL	QUARTILE
		Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria	Contemplation of all the relevant studies	Evaluation of the quality and/or Validity of the Studies	Adequated description of the basis of data/studies		
ES_05	[A6]	1	1	1	1	4	4th
ES_11	[A14]	1	1	1	1	4	
ES_14	[A17]	1	0,5	1	1	3,5	
ES_18	[A21]	1	1	1	0,5	3,5	
ES_20	[A24]	0,5	1	1	1	3,5	
ES_07	[A9]	1	1	0	1	3	3 rd
ES_08	[A10]	1	1	0	1	3	
ES_10	[A12]	1	1	0	1	3	
ES_13	[A16]	1	1	0	1	3	
ES_15	[A18]	1	0,5	1	0,5	3	
ES_19	[A22]	1	1	0	1	3	
ES_02	[A2]	0,5	1	0	1	2,5	
ES_12	[A15]	1	0,5	0	1	2,5	
ES_04	[A4]	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	2	2 nd

ES_o6	[A7]	1	0,5	0	0,5	2	
ES_16	[A19]	1	0,5	0	0,5	2	
ES_17	[A20]	1	0,5	0	1	2	
ES_o3	[A3]	0,5	0,5	0	0,5	1,5	
ES_o1	[A1]	0	0,5	0	0,5	1	1 st
ES_o9	[A11]	0	0,5	0	0,5	1	